

Analysis of teacher organization commitment in Tangerang Regency public junior high school

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the influence of locus of control and supervision channeled to an organization as a whole on organizational commitment and examines and describes the influence of locus of control and supervision on organizational commitment. The instrument uses questionnaires. The sample is determined by proportional stratified random sampling. From 268 teacher samples from 33 public junior high schools in Tangerang Regency, data analysis used structural equation modeling (SEM). The findings show that locus of control and supervision significantly affect organizational commitment, and locus of control significantly affects supervision. These findings prove that the locus of control and supervision of teachers can act as indicators of organizational commitment. The practical implication of this research is to provide knowledge and information for teachers and school management to increase organizational commitment by applying the concepts of locus of control and teacher supervision.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The quality of education serves as a benchmark for a country's human resources. The quality of education can be observed through the learning materials present in the curriculum, syllabus, lesson plans, and classroom teaching activities [1]. However, the quality of learning in Indonesia is still low, necessitating urgent actions to catch up with other countries [2]. One solution to bridge the educational gap between Indonesia and developed countries worldwide is to improve the quality and standards of education [3]. Educational institutions must meet the expectations of parents and the state by maximizing students' potential through adequate education [4]. These institutions should have specific programs and objectives that are well-managed and achieved. After conducting observations at Tangerang Public Junior High School, researchers identified crucial and pressing issues that must be addressed promptly. Failure to address these issues may hinder teaching-learning, leading to unachieved school objectives. The problems include organizational commitment, locus of control, and teacher supervision (based on observations at Tangerang Public Junior High School). Regarding organizational commitment, the following issues were found: i) lack of management support, ii) heavy workload, and iii) unclear roles and responsibilities. As for locus of control: i) dominance of external locus of control, resulting in difficulty managing teaching, ii) low self-

confidence in teacher decision-making, and iii) dependence on external feedback. Lastly, regarding teacher supervision: i) insufficient frequency and quality of supervision, limited feedback, ii) lack of focus on individual teacher needs, and iii) inadequate support and constructive feedback.

Educational institutions require harmony in carrying out their primary duties and functions. A good relationship between education providers, colleagues, and teachers with principals, principals, and other administrators is crucial for completing tasks [5]. Organizational commitment is deemed necessary [6] and vital for educational institutions [7]. The success of educational institutions lies in providing services and satisfaction to consumers or the community [8]. Teachers and educators must focus on teaching, assessing, training, and evaluating students in early childhood, primary, and secondary education [9]. This is the primary responsibility of teachers and educators, as stated in article 1, paragraph 1 [10]. Organizational commitment is crucial for the teaching profession because students are evolving beings; thus, teacher presence in the classroom is mandatory and cannot be ignored [11]. The issues mentioned above result in decreasing motivation, limited teacher development potential, commitment, student progress, low locus of control, frustration, ineffective teacher supervision, and teacher dissatisfaction. Therefore, considering the mentioned problems, it becomes essential for researchers to address organizational commitment, locus of control, and teacher supervision as they strive to contribute to the field of education and enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of the teaching-learning process at Tangerang Public Junior High school, specifically, and for all educational institutions in Indonesia in general.

Teachers do not have a high desire to follow the institution's rules to achieve goals, are not loyal to the institution, and do not have emotional ties to the institution [12]. More than 50% of school teachers in Tangerang Regency said that teacher behavior that hinders school progress does not prioritize the interests of the school [13]. Among the behaviors that hinder school progress is that teachers do not prioritize loyalty and school interests [14]. Teachers ignore school goals, do not want to know about school programs, and are not willing when there are meetings outside school operating hours [15]. The above behavior examples indicate weak organizational commitment [16]. However, organizational commitment will grow within the institution if teachers do not fulfill their primary duties and responsibilities [17]. Therefore, adding organizational commitment to the learning process in educational institutions should not be taken lightly [18]. Based on this description, it can be concluded that teachers who provide organizational commitment bring far more significant benefits than teachers who only carry out basic tasks [19]. Unfortunately, not all teachers want to do well in organizational commitments [20]. Organizational commitment in educational institutions often does not appear as one indicator that the school is not progressing for the next few years [21]. Teachers do not participate in the implementation of school programs if not requested, teacher permission at meetings held outside the school teaching and learning activities, and do not achieve the learning targets set by the school [22]. These are evidence of actual behavior in educational institutions [23]. Every individual, especially a teacher, needs a locus of control in performing their primary duties and daily functions [24]. Locus of control is self-control at work [25]. Locus of control is a condition in which a person can control his successes and failures in tasks [26]. However, in practice, many teachers still carry out their duties with positive expectations, which means that the Locus of control over private schools is still low. The locus of control is necessary to support the living needs of the organization's members [27].

Therefore, supervision can be improved by locus of control [28]. This can lead to teacher behavior that is still based on the desire to survive and serve the organization to achieve organizational goals, so it is a necessity for educational institutions to progress in the present and the future (organizational commitment) [29]. Supervision is another need for teachers that is no less important in advancing educational institutions [30]. Teacher supervision is essential because teacher supervision will be given input and improvements in teaching to high quality [31]. This is inseparable from his considerable interest and attention to the field of work he is engaged in and dealing directly with students [32]. With entire interest and responsibility, an educator or teacher will devote himself as well as possible so that the desired results of his work are not only for his satisfaction but also for students and the surrounding community. The explanation above shows how dizzy the organization's commitment to an educational institution is. This study examines how the relationship between the locus of control and supervision variable indicators affects teacher organizational commitment [33]. The unit of analysis of this research is a public junior high school teacher in Tangerang Regency, Banten Province. It is hoped that the findings of this research on organizational commitment can improve and develop teachers' performance and directly impact the achievement of programs and goals so that school progress is a certainty.

2. METHOD

2.1. Data and research sample collection

The information used in these investigations was collected through questionnaires that followed the concept of each variable in the study [34]. Each questionnaire has three variables: the organizational

commitment variable consists of 30 questions [35]. The locus of control variable comprised 35 questions, and the supervision variable comprised 30 questions. After verifying the effectiveness and consistency of the questionnaire with the results of the validity and reliability of the 0.05 r-table, a significant level was obtained where the question criteria were considered valid if the table results were significant and reliable if the table results were not significant [36]. The calculation is the test result of SPSS using the Pearson product-moment formula. R-table is the product moment table of the coefficient (R) [37].

This procedure involves calculating the difference between the r-value in the table and the r-value attributed to statistical analysis [38]. It produces relevant data with 27 questions about organizational commitment, 30 questions about locus of control, and 28 questions regarding supervision. A valid and reliable questionnaire was used to collect and distribute information to 268 participants. The sample size of 268 respondents came from a population of 814, using the Slovin formula [39].

To collect a sample of 268 respondents, the authors used a proportional random sampling technique. The sampling steps are as follows: first, the population of interest is determined: all 814 public junior high school teachers in Tangerang Regency. Next, a number is generated that combines the first four digits of the phone numbers of each of the 814 teachers. Finally, random sampling [40] was conducted to select 268 out of 814 teachers as research samples.

2.2. Instrument

The instrument section of each variable includes a conceptual description, a practical description, and instructions on how to implement the variable [39]. In a conceptual definition, each variable is derived from some idea conceived by experts. In the operational definition, each variable is derived from expert thinking, along with a subject and metric that measures how much each variable affects the other variables [41]. In the instrument manual, questions are derived from the metrics associated with each variable [42]. In addition, data comes from instruments that have proven accurate and reliable, and it is necessary to verify the validity of data collected using such instruments. Likert scales represent all variables [43].

Organizational commitment is considered an individual behavior measured as a choice rather than a formal evaluation and overall promotes an organization's effective operation. Reliability measurement ($r=0.33$). The locus of control is the extent of teachers' self-control in their organizational duties. The reliability ($r=0.93$) measurement of supervision is estimated as supervision and improvement made by the superior, the principal, or the school superintendent assigned by the education office. Reliability measurement ($r=0.88$).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Measurement model

Validity is true to character based on evidence or logic [44]. This becomes important because it is information derived from facts for measuring pre-existing concepts in research procedures for measurement. In the Social science research process, measurements can be based on characteristics that are implemented indirectly. Researchers use confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to analyze research findings [45]. CFA is applied to test models where measurement models are formed based on theoretical frameworks [46]. It focuses on whether the conceptualized indicators are consistent and correct and which are most important in shaping the research construct [47]. Therefore, the evaluation of the validity of the five constructs is carried out by considering the results of the fit model index from structural equation modeling (SEM) [48]. Normed fit index (NFI)=0.993, goodness of fit statistic (GFI)=0.331, root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)=0.0547, normed chi-square (X^2/df)=2.024, non-normed fit index (NNFI)=0.988 and comparative fit index (CFI)=0.991. As seen in Table 1, all models correspond to acceptable index values. The construct reliability (CR) and variance extracted (VE) values of the supervision variable VE=0.721, CR=0.962, locus of control VE=0.753, CR=0.950, organizational commitment VE=0.680, CR=0.993. All variables meet the requirement that the value of VE must be more than 0.5, and the value of CR must be more than 0.78.

3.2. Structural modeling assessment

The structural model analysis uses Lisrel 8.72 for calculation validation by comparing the existing index in Lisrel with the calculation results. Statistical calculations were not performed due to the large sample size. This study refers to the (X^2/df ; $2 < X^2/df < 5$), (NFI; > 0.9), (GFI; > 0.90), (RMSEA; < 0.10), relative fit index (RFI; > 0.9), and comparative fit index (CFI; > 0.9). The results showed that all structural models were accepted [48]: $X^2/df=2.014$, NFI=0.993, GFI=0.331, RMSEA=0.0547, RFI=0.966, and CFI=0.991. The results of the analysis of Lisrel's calculations show the suitability of the model and the significance of the causality of each variable. The relationship between variable measurement and theoretical variables is often the same or supports the results of previous studies. Analysis of the structural model to support hypothesis 1 found that supervision positively influenced teachers' organizational commitments ($\gamma_{23}=0.28$, $t=4.78$) supported by other researchers [49]. The locus of control appears to have a weak

relationship but significantly affects teacher organizational commitment ($\gamma_{13}=0.20$, $t=4.21$), and hypothesis 2 is supported [50]. Locus of control significantly affects teacher supervision ($\gamma_{12}=0.32$, $t=5.33$), and these findings support hypothesis 3, previous research also supports these empirical, analytical findings that explain how locus of control affects supervision.

Table 1. CFA

Latent construct	CR	VE
Supervision	0.96	0.72
Locus of control	0.95	0.75
Organization commitment	0.99	0.68
X ² /do=2.024, RMSEA=0.0547, GFI=0.331, NFI=0.993, CFI=0.991 and RFI=0.966		

4. CONCLUSION

In the discussion, it can be seen that the results of this study are used in verifying the structural interaction between the locus of control variables, administrative supervision, and organizational commitment. In addition, this study aims to look carefully and deeply at the influence of the independent variable (organizational supervision and locus of control) on the dependent variable (organizational commitment). First, the author reviews and synthesizes the theories and concepts of all variables, creates indicators, and forms research models. This study used a literature review and empirical analysis to verify the research model and answer the hypothesis. This study's results show that the organizational commitment variable is significantly influenced by teacher supervision (hypothesis 1). Therefore, it is recognized that in improving organizational commitment, teacher supervision is a variable that plays an essential role in implementing policies in schools. The locus of control has also been shown to increase organizational commitment (hypothesis 2), consistent with previous studies findings. Teacher supervision is influenced by the locus of control (hypothesis 3). This means that teacher supervision is a factor in developing the teacher's locus of control. The better the implementation of teacher supervision through distributive, procedural, and interactional supervision, the more it will boost the locus of control. The findings of previous studies support this finding. The locus of control influences organizational commitment, consistent with previous research. This means the higher the locus of control level, the higher the teacher organization's commitment.

Briefly, the findings of this study suggest that several variables, including teacher supervision and locus of control, can influence organizational commitment. This study aims to verify suggested models based on theoretical studies and concepts from scientific journals and handbooks on organizational behavior, human resource management, and management and research design. The authors note some of the implications suggested by previous research, including improving the quality of procedural supervision and the methods and approaches applied in implementing decisions. Decisions made by schools need to take into account the expectations and needs of teachers and increase consistency, loyalty, and transparency in education management, including facilities, finances, educators, or education personnel in schools and national education. Moreover, it can be deciphered from the findings that proper teacher supervision for teachers produces feelings of happiness and even organizational commitment. So, an indicator that teachers have organizational commitment is the fulfillment of teacher supervision, who can carry out their primary duties and functions thoroughly and well. This can undoubtedly improve teachers' ability to have a positive attitude towards their work.

Locus of control refers to a teacher's self-control over success and failure in his duties. A teacher under administrative or organizational supervision will likely show higher dedication and enthusiasm. Activities include problem-solving skills, task completion, and all day-to-day aspects of a teacher's work. A teacher with a locus of control will demonstrate perseverance in gaining commitment to the organization, enjoying his work, having personal responsibility, having high expectations of work, and motivation to complete tasks on time. A positive teacher locus of control will reflect perseverance in gaining commitment to the organization, enjoying work, having personal responsibility, and having high expectations for achieving and completing tasks on time. Commitment to the organization contributes to teacher performance, enabling them to provide optimal service. It can be revealed that the correct locus of control can increase commitment to the organization, encourage a teacher to take control of relationships with colleagues, and overcome working conditions that are influenced by internal and external psychological factors. Commitment to the organization is influenced by distributive supervision and procedural and interactional behavior that supports and holds responsibility for the organization. All these aspects support job performance. The collaboration between teacher supervision and locus of control implemented in schools by teachers and organizations is expected to positively impact commitment to the organization, which in turn can improve the quality of teaching, school management, and educational development in schools.

This research contributes to the field of education, especially in the development of educators and teachers, so that the process of managing educational institutions can be more effective and efficient. If human resources in the school have good organizational commitment behavior, they can optimize learning activities. This research certainly has limitations. First, although the collected sample represents the population, the object of study is only public teachers. Future studies are suggested to explore these findings with greater scope and depth.

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